

Arabic Transliteration — “Mics in the ears” experimental procedure Translittération arabe — dispositif expérimental « Des micros dans les oreilles »

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Lettres arabes <i>Arabic letters</i>	Translittération DIN 31635 <i>DIN 31635 Transliteration</i> sauf pour/except for ق, ة, ع, غ, خ, ج	Prononciation en arabe littéral (API) <i>Literal Arabic Pronunciation (API)</i>
ء	ʾ	[ʔ]
ا	ā	[a:]
ب	b	[b]
ت	t	[t]
ث	ṭ	[θ]
ج	j/g	[dʒ] [g]
ح	ḥ	[ħ]
خ	x	[x]
د	d	[d]
ذ	ḏ	[ð]
ر	r	[r]
ز	z	[z]
س	s	[s]
ش	š	[ʃ]
ص	ṣ	[sʕ]
ض	ḏ	[dʕ]
ط	ṭ	[tʕ]
ظ	ẓ	[ðʕ]
ع	ɛ	[ʕ]
غ	ɣ	[ʁ]
ف	f	[f]
ق	q/q ^h	[q] [ʔ]
ك	k	[k]
ل	l	[l]
م	m	[m]
ن	n	[n]
ه	h	[h]
ة	a	[ʰ] ([t])
و	w (ū si voyelle longue/ <i>if long vowel</i>)	[w] ([u:])
ي	y (ī si voyelle longue/ <i>if long vowel</i>)	[j] ([i:])